

PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES TO DEVELOP CREATIVE THINKING, CREATIVITY, COMMUNICATION AND COOPERATION SKILLS IN STUDENTS

Islamova K.T.

Tashkent military academic lyceum "School of Temurbeklar", senior teacher on geography

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Abstract. *This article discusses about the pedagogical possibilities of developing students' creative thinking, creativity, communication and cooperation skills, research, experiences, and accumulated knowledge in this regard.*

Keywords: *creativity, speed, responsiveness, cooperation, individuality, talent, communication, cooperation, creative thinking.*

It is known that the development of creative activity of an individual is gaining special relevance today. The need for young people who can make non-standard decisions with their own strong views on life is growing. For this purpose, special attention is paid to the formation of "creative thinking" mechanisms in all educational institutions. This indicates the strong need to form and regularly develop creative thinking skills in every learner at all stages of continuous education. Special attention is paid to this issue in "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" [1]. For this, there is a strong need to update the means of teaching subjects during the pedagogical process in creative thinking. Such a need requires organizing the cooperative activities of teachers and students in a new context. Textbooks, educational literature, computer technologies, and innovative methods of teaching can be included among didactic tools that shape students' creative thinking. It consists in increasing student's creative thinking index, freeing him from frontal tasks, opening a wide path for his independent thinking, giving him the opportunity to create innovations, and helping him to choose an individual educational direction for himself. Educational materials, questions and tasks, and scientific literature can be included among the didactic tools that help to develop student's creative skills. Pedagogical subjects have favorable opportunities for this. Teachers and parents should always support students' creative skills and create favorable conditions for the development of these skills. Creativity ensures the manifestation of student's creative powers and internal capabilities. Our thinking ancestors paid special attention to the formation of creative thinking in young people. If these approaches are brought to the minds of students in the process of teaching "History of Pedagogy", "Didactics", they will support them in the knowledge they impart to schoolchildren in the future and contribute to the formation of creative thinking mechanisms of students. Because, in these books, attention is focused on the scientific justification of the aspects of creativity related to mental processes. They were able to justify the creativity of a person in connection with the processes of mental cognition, emotional cognition, empirical cognition, and rational cognition. A person achieves the main goals set for himself as a result of creative thinking. His views, beliefs, assumptions are the product of creative thinking. Creative thinking is a comprehensive phenomenon by its nature. Creative thinking people can contribute to the development of the nation and society. A person's creative thinking skills determine his lifestyle and are manifested in his daily social activities. New inventions, examples of creativity, are the product of creative thinking. At the same time, thanks

to thinking, new ideas and hypotheses are put forward, research is carried out. Creativity (lat. creation - creativity) - the ability to create something new, unique, create an artistic form, a mental process that leads to thinking, ideas and solutions; creative ability, which describes a person's readiness to create and accept new ideas [4]. Accordingly, creativity is an expression of goal-oriented creative behavior of students, which includes the creation of original ideas, enthusiasm, diligence, aesthetic attitude to the environment, self-awareness, reflection, etc. includes a set of personal qualities. Thus, the creative thinking of teachers is directly related to promptness, responsiveness, mobility, and diligence. By teaching students to think creatively, there is an opportunity to show their professional abilities and talents. Pedagogical processes in the classroom and outside the classroom are of great importance. Along with all other tools, teacher's professional skills and competence play an important role in teaching students to think creatively. In this process, it is recommended to widely use heuristic tasks used in the teaching of category subjects in pedagogy. Heuristic tasks play an important role in the formation of creative skills of a professional nature in students. Because, while solving these tasks, students will be able to search creatively. Heuristic tasks encourage students to search creatively and show the result of creative activity. Regular monitoring and improvement of students' creative activities requires special professional skills and creativity from teachers. In the national educational program, priority is given to teaching students to think creatively. As a result of creative thinking, working communication and educational cooperation between teachers and students is created. This technology serves to develop a creative environment aimed at the formation of a creative personality, to increase the quality and efficiency of education. Cooperative pedagogy reflects the following important ideas: turning the school of knowledge into a school of education, putting student's personality at the center of the holistic education system, the humanistic nature of education, the formation of universal and national values, the development of child's creative ability and individuality, individual and collective carrying out education in harmony. Cooperative education is based on the following target directions:

- organization of relations based on educational cooperation, denying the pedagogical requirement;
- individual approach to students based on humanitarian ideas;
- achieving professional and spiritual unity during the educational process. What does cooperative learning give the student?
 - enriches student's learning process;
 - provides students with cognitive information (education to expand the scope of knowledge about the environment, develop cognitive needs);
 - makes students eager to learn the material; (3)

Teachers should create favorable pedagogical situations in order to form creative thinking skills in students. In order to teach students to think creatively, teachers are required to create a number of favorable situations during the learning process and gradually increase the number of educational tasks that serve creative thinking.

1. Creating learning situations that provide students with detailed information about creative phenomena and scientific concepts. Formation of motives for students' creative assimilation of educational materials. Creating conditions for students to work more independently in the learning process.

2. Expanding the scope of creative works of students in the process of teaching the subjects of the category. Asking students challenging questions that require creative thinking. Encouraging students to find multiple solutions to the same problem. Creating didactic situations that allow creative work on educational materials. Setting individual tasks for students, taking into account their level of creative thinking.

3. Presentation of several methods of solving educational tasks in the process of teaching subjects of the pedagogical category.

In order to form creative thinking skills in students, it is required to provide them with new educational materials, to develop the ability to find solutions to problems, and to arm them with methods of creative approach to solving problems. For this purpose, it is envisaged to develop students' creative thinking, the ability to perceive pedagogical events and problems. Performing self-development tasks creatively is a product of creative thinking. Creative thinking encourages students to create innovations. It is based on examples of creative works created by students. Creative works show students' ability to think creatively. In most cases, creative skills and intellectual abilities of students do not differ from each other. Creative thinking differs from intelligence according to its pedagogical and psychological aspects. And creative thinking means positive thinking. Intellect (lat. intellectus - mind, perception, intelligence) is the activity of a person based on the full knowledge of the essence of the event and manifested through it; human mental capacity; the ability to accurately reflect and change life, the environment in the mind, think, read, learn, know the world and accept social experience; the ability to solve various issues, come to a decision, act rationally, foresee events.

The process of developing students' creative thinking skills has a complex pedagogical character. Accordingly, this process requires systematic presentation of educational materials. The formation of creative thinking skills in students creates a pedagogical basis for the manifestation of individual's creative ability. Creative thinking expands creative possibilities. As a result, students' learning opportunities expand, self-development motives are created. The ability to search for information, sort it and work on it is directly related to creative thinking. The goal of creative thinking is that the main goal of forming mastered educational materials and information at various levels is directly related to the formation of life and professional competencies in them. The content of pedagogical education is to develop creative thinking skills, to inculcate the social experience of Uzbek people into student's mind. As a result, the ability to positively perceive reality is formed. As a result, their educational activities will stabilize and their creative possibilities will expand. In the educational process, with the help of innovative technologies, creative thinking skills develop rapidly, and a creative environment is created. In this context, an important feature of the educational process is its focus on creative thinking. In the process of teaching subjects of pedagogical category, the question arises as to how much space should be allocated to the formation of creative thinking skills in students. In the process of pedagogical education of an innovative nature, the step-by-step development of logical and creative skills of students is envisaged. In this process, teachers pay special attention to the use of mechanisms of formation of creative thinking motives in students. For this, they strive to improve the mechanisms and functions of achieving educational goals. To achieve this goal, they select and systematize the necessary educational tools, didactic materials, questions and tasks. As a result, the educational process is directed to the formation of creative thinking skills, and it is directed to the implementation of a creative paradigm, departing from the functional paradigm of education.

Based on the goals of the pedagogical process, its design and organization expands students' opportunities for creative thinking. Pupils' readiness to think creatively helps them to develop knowledge motives.

The personality of the teacher, his intelligence, his attitude to science, and his ability to explain the studied material in an interesting way are important for the development of students' creative abilities and talents. The influence on the development of students' working skills and their interest in learning depends on the teacher.

In the development of creative ability and talent, the ability of the teacher to light the sparks of curiosity in the student in a certain field of knowledge and work, and to awaken his active mental and practical activity in this direction plays an important role. K. E. Sialkovsky, the founder of interplanetary rocket science, worked with this idea since he was sixteen years old. Due to his health, he was forced to leave the gymnasium teaching, and became friends with books. From A. Gounod's textbook "Physics", he first learned about the flight of balloons. Impressed by what he has read, an inquisitive teenager tries to make a balloon. Then he had the idea of creating jet-powered spacecraft for interplanetary travel, which he devoted his entire life to realizing. In order to develop the creative ability and talent of students, creative problem solving in the educational process, motivation to master the studied material, individual work with well-educated students, and educational load to better illuminate their intellectual potential increase is of great importance. Maintaining these conditions creates the necessary conditions for the development of students' abilities and creative tendencies during the educational process. If the training is organized correctly, it will serve to improve the culture of mental work. In this process, students acquire and improve educational work skills and abilities, learn to maintain a reasonable schedule of work and rest, thereby developing their thinking, memory, and creative abilities. But the main thing in this process is the education of a scientific outlook and moral-aesthetic culture. Solving this problem requires special attention from the teacher. The point is that if the theoretical and practical nature of knowledge is expressed as much as possible, and the activities of students are directly aimed at discovering them, the worldview and moral aesthetic ideas contained in this knowledge will emerge with clarity. It is necessary to reveal the ideological and moral-aesthetic content of the studied material, to understand and assimilate knowledge, and to develop practical skills in the development of students' creative abilities and talents. At the same time, the teacher should achieve a deep understanding and firm assimilation of students' worldview and moral-aesthetic ideas and conclusions at the same time.[2]

The problem of forming a culture of communication in teacher's professional activity is solved based on the needs and requirements of the individual society. In our republic, various scientific researches have been carried out in different periods regarding the unique ethnopsychological qualities of the teaching profession, feelings, abilities, working methods, ways of acquiring the secrets of pedagogical skills, interpersonal communication culture. It should be noted that the realization of the educational potential of communication culture is largely determined by the personal qualities of the teacher. The method of pedagogical communication culture, chosen correctly in all respects, in accordance with teacher's spiritual level, unique characteristics, helps to solve the following set of tasks: first, special attention to each student in communication and harmony with the class team simplifies the general communication process, prepares the ground for teacher's free pedagogical activity, easily resolves conflict situations; secondly, organizing interaction with each student on the basis of free communication, choosing

pedagogical and psychological communication methods that are compatible with their age characteristics, opens the way to know their psyche, to "enter" their inner world; thirdly, the moral and ethical standards of the teacher in pedagogical communication are the key to success, increase the effectiveness of education, ensure teacher's satisfaction and peace of mind in all stages of communication. The methodology of formation of individual styles of communication culture of the teacher with students includes the following stages:

1. Study of individual personal characteristics of the culture of communication with students: independent analysis of personal characteristics of students, giving a comprehensive description of students' internal capabilities, proper organization of teacher's culture of communication.

2. Immediate elimination of deficiencies in personal communication: immediately finding measures to eliminate the problems, not to be rude to students in any situation, elimination of negative situations such as disregarding the personality of the student.

3. The teacher should choose the most convenient methods of communication culture for him: he should develop a model of communication culture similar to his pedagogical activity, self-observation and regular comparison of achievements and shortcomings in communication, continuous use of opportunities of our national spirituality, customs and traditions in communication.

4. Not to deviate from the rules of pedagogical activity in the culture of communication: to develop a communication system suitable for the individual characteristics of each student, to recognize the educational effect and effectiveness of communication, to demonstrate pedagogical skills based on the culture of communication. In order to improve professional skills, young teachers who are just starting their pedagogical activities should regularly work on forming a culture of communication with students. Pedagogical communication culture in the organization of the educational process is a force that leads the direct interaction of teachers and students towards a certain goal. In this place, it is necessary to emphasize that the teacher should pay attention to the following situations:

- the teacher should observe the culture of communication from the first educational activities, in this process he should plan the daily interaction with the teacher and the group of students depending on the situation, every action, paying attention to the tone of words, mastering the best features of traditional communication;

- on the basis of communication, to record various situations in the class group, to evaluate students' behavior by comparing it with the previous state and the state after the educational activity;

Analyzing the results of one's communication style from a critical point of view and constantly eliminating shortcomings. It is not enough to know its conditions for the effective development of the culture of pedagogical communication, it is the beginning of interaction with students and the exchange of ideas typical of the "teacher-student" tradition.

A young teacher who adheres to the culture of pedagogical communication, which is a unique quality of professional activity, must embody the following characteristics:

- views of a high level of spirituality, strong and stable faith, corresponding to the socio-political requirements and needs of our country.

a socio-politically active person who is loyal to the ideals of our state, the national idea and the ideology of independence, patriotism, self-sacrifice;

- the formation of sincere love for students, the ability to understand all their needs, interests, motivations and behaviors;

- Pedagogical observation of events occurring in society, events occurring in the world, nature, existence, interpersonal, inter-group, inter-ethnic relations, the ability to strive for innovation, creative research;

- rational understanding of the characteristics of people's actions and relationships in all aspects of pedagogical activity, forming a reflexive attitude towards one's own activities;

- to react rationally and intelligently to any emergency situations, to news happening in society, and to social and economic changes, to be able to set the right goals for oneself, to draw up a plan.

In order to quickly eliminate various conflicting situations that may arise in the process of communication with students, the teacher should first of all rely on his talent and pedagogical skills. Achievements achieved on the basis of pedagogical dialogue are the product of teacher's creative work. Undoubtedly, there are negative and positive aspects of this work. It is necessary to rationally evaluate every situation, to plan it correctly, to organize intelligent communication in educational processes. The lack of mutual understanding between the teacher and the students in communication, the poverty of the means of communication, the lack of treatment according to the mentality of each student, the same mandatory obedience to everyone, the emotionally negative order that calls the students to a narrow discipline form of communication causes constant conflicts. In order to create a well-founded system of working on pedagogical communication methods, each teacher should solve the difficulties by analyzing his own problems and shortcomings. The general direction of all exercises related to pedagogical dialogue is to use tools that help to develop the personal feelings of each dialogue participant, to develop skills in existing pedagogical situations. It is necessary to determine the subjective views of some students on the communication, to define the tasks necessary for the rational resolution of the communication with this student, to correct his behavior or to create a mood of confidence in him.

In these situations, a set of systematic means of mutual actions can be defined as follows:

- education in the process of communication
- ability to anticipate the possibilities of response action of the subject being educated in the process of communication;
- obtaining tools that cause psychological barriers and negative views in the object;
- having several models of communication that can be used depending on the change in the situation;
- listening to the opinions of the student, agreeing to their opinions, developing the ability to sympathize with them;
- evaluation of the results of interaction and comparison of achievements and shortcomings on the basis of pedagogical and psychological tools.

In conclusion, it should be said that the nature of pedagogical activity and pedagogical dialogue is inextricably linked with teacher's personality, ideological political level, professional training and desire to know, which is reflected in his views and behavior. In addition to these basic characteristics, the general and other abilities of the teacher, the nature of his inclinations, temporary mental states, as well as accumulated experience are important. One of the professional aspects of teacher's personality and ways of self-education is manifested in the exercises to analyze his qualities and feelings, as well as the stable characteristics of pedagogical activities and communication, the level of teacher's knowledge and the results achieved as a result of his upbringing. (2)

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